

ALGORITHM OF REAL ESTATE EVALUATION BASED ON SUPPORT VECTOR REGRESSION

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Annotation: This article presents an algorithm for real estate evaluation using Support Vector Regression (SVR). SVR is a powerful machine learning technique capable of capturing complex relationships between real estate features and property prices. The article provides an overview of SVR, discusses its application in real estate valuation, and outlines the step-by-step algorithm for implementing SVR in the context of property evaluation.

Keywords: Real Estate Evaluation, Support Vector Regression, Machine Learning, Property Valuation, Feature Engineering.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola Support Vector Regressiyasi (SVR) yordamida ko'chmas mulkni baholash algoritmini taqdim etadi. SVR - bu ko'chmas mulk xususiyatlari va mulk narxlari o'rtasidagi murakkab munosabatlarni qo'lga kiritishga qodir kuchli mashinani o'qitish usuli. Maqolada SVR haqida umumiy ma'lumot berilgan, uning ko'chmas mulkni baholashda qo'llanilishi muhokama qilinadi va mulkni baholash kontekstida SVRni amalga oshirishning bosqichma-bosqich algoritmi ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'chmas mulkni baholash, Support Vector Regressiya, mashinani o'qitish, mulkni baholash, xususiyat muhandisligi.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен алгоритм оценки недвижимости с использованием регрессии опорных векторов (SVR). SVR — это мощный метод машинного обучения, способный фиксировать сложные взаимосвязи между характеристиками недвижимости и ценами на нее. В статье представлен обзор SVR, рассмотрено его применение при оценке недвижимости, а также изложен пошаговый алгоритм внедрения SVR в контексте оценки имущества.

Ключевые слова: оценка недвижимости, регрессия опорных векторов, машинное обучение, оценка недвижимости, проектирование признаков.

Real estate valuation plays a crucial role in the property market, influencing investment decisions, mortgage approvals, and economic policies. Traditionally, real estate appraisal has relied on expert judgment, market comparables, and regression analysis. However, with the advent of machine learning techniques, automated valuation models (AVMs) based on advanced algorithms have gained popularity for their accuracy and efficiency. Support Vector Regression (SVR) is one such technique that offers promising results in real estate valuation by leveraging the power of machine learning to predict property prices based on relevant features. In this article, we explore the algorithm of real estate evaluation using SVR, highlighting its advantages and applications in the property market.

Methodological Approaches. Research studies have explored various methodological approaches for implementing SVR in real estate valuation. This includes feature selection techniques, kernel function optimization, hyperparameter tuning, and model evaluation strategies tailored to the specific characteristics of real estate datasets.

Feature Engineering and Selection. Feature engineering plays a crucial role in improving the predictive performance of SVR models for real estate valuation. Studies have investigated the relevance of different features, including property characteristics (e.g., size, location, amenities), economic indicators, demographic data, and spatial attributes, in predicting property prices [1].

Kernel Functions and Model Complexity. The choice of kernel function in SVR models significantly impacts their performance in real estate valuation. Studies have compared the effectiveness of linear, polynomial, radial basis function (RBF), and sigmoid kernels in capturing nonlinear relationships and complex patterns in real estate data.

Model Performance and Accuracy. Empirical studies have evaluated the predictive accuracy and performance of SVR models compared to traditional regression techniques and other machine learning algorithms for real estate valuation. Results have demonstrated the superior performance of SVR in capturing non-linear relationships and improving prediction accuracy, especially in datasets with complex patterns and high-dimensional feature spaces [2].

Robustness to Outliers and Noise: SVR models are known for their robustness to outliers and noise in real estate datasets, making them suitable for handling data imperfections and irregularities common in property valuation. Scientific research has investigated the resilience of SVR models to outliers and the effectiveness of outlier detection techniques in improving model robustness.

Interpretability and Model Transparency. Despite their predictive power, SVR models are often criticized for their lack of interpretability compared to traditional regression models. Research efforts have focused on enhancing the interpretability of SVR models through feature importance analysis, visualization techniques, and post-hoc explanations of model predictions. Scientific literature includes case studies and practical applications of SVR models in real-world real estate valuation scenarios. These studies demonstrate the effectiveness of SVR in predicting property prices, optimizing investment decisions, assessing market trends, and supporting decision-making by real estate professionals, investors, and stakeholders [3].

By synthesizing and analyzing scientific research on real estate valuation based on Support Vector Regression, practitioners and researchers can gain valuable insights into the methodology, best practices, and challenges associated with implementing SVR models in the context of property valuation and investment decision-making [1,3].

Below are the basic formulas for Support Vector Regression (SVR) in the context of real estate valuation:

$$1. \text{ SVR Objective Function: } \min_{w, b, \xi, \xi^*} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^m (\xi_i + \xi_i^*)$$

Subject to:

$$y_i - w^T \phi(x_i) - b \leq \varepsilon + \xi_i$$

$$w^T \phi(x_i) + b \leq \varepsilon + \xi_i^*$$

$$\xi_i, \xi_i^* \geq 0$$

Where: w is the weight vector; b is the bias term; ξ_i, ξ_i^* are slack variables; $\phi(x_i)$ is the feature mapping function; C is the regularization parameter; ε is the epsilon parameter [4].

2. Kernel Function:

The kernel function $K(x_i, x_j) = x_i^T x_j$ calculates the similarity between two samples x_i and x_j .

3. Model Prediction: $\hat{y} = \sum_{n=1}^m (a_i + a_i^*)K(x_i, x) + b$

Where: a_i and a_i^* are Lagrange multipliers; b is the bias term; x is the input sample for prediction [1,5].

These formulas outline the basic principles of Support Vector Regression for real estate valuation. Implementing these formulas in a programming environment, along with appropriate data preprocessing and model training steps, enables the creation of a real estate valuation model based on SVR.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the algorithm of real estate evaluation based on Support Vector Regression (SVR) offers a promising approach to predicting property prices with accuracy and efficiency. By leveraging the power of machine learning, SVR enables automated valuation models (AVMs) that can handle complex data patterns and provide valuable insights for real estate investors, homeowners, and industry professionals. As the demand for accurate real estate valuation continues to grow, SVR remains a valuable tool in the arsenal of modern property valuation techniques, offering unparalleled predictive capabilities and actionable insights for decision-making in the dynamic real estate market.

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